

Fortifying Indulgence: Development and Nutritional Profiling of Fruit Juice-Enhanced Dark Chocolate

Sweta Mondal¹, Indira Dutta², Avery Sengupta^{2*}

¹Department of Food and Nutrition, University of Kalyani, Kalyani, Nadia

²Department of Dietetics and Applied Nutrition, AIASK, Amity University Kolkata

Chocolate is considered one of the most consumed delicacies worldwide. These days, prebiotic, probiotic, and high-cocoa polyphenol-rich chocolates are gaining more attention. High chocolate consumption has the potential to turn unhealthy foods into highly functional foods. Fortifying dark chocolate with watermelon and sweet lime (sweet lime) might enhance their nutritional properties. This study was conducted to assess the impact of adding watermelon and sweet lime juice on the antioxidant properties of dark chocolate. Four types of test samples were prepared using different sweetening agents such as brown sugar, jaggery, and honey. The effects of these sweeteners on the chocolate's nutritional parameters were also evaluated. Several analytical methods were used in this study, including proximate analysis, polyphenol content measurement, antioxidant activity assays, and mineral content analysis. Two different methods—DPPH scavenging activity and reducing power—were used to measure antioxidant activity. The results showed that, compared to plain dark chocolate used as a control, chocolate enriched with watermelon and sweet lime juice exhibited higher polyphenol levels, antioxidant capacity, and mineral content.

Keywords: Dark chocolate, Enrichment, Fortification, Watermelon Juice, Sweet Lime Juice, Brown sugar, Jaggery, Honey

INTRODUCTION

Chocolate is a popular, lip-smacking sweet among all age groups. Its consumption rate continues to grow around the world year after year (Samanta et al., 2022). Chocolate can be classified into dark, milk, and white, depending on their ingredients and production. Dark chocolate is made from cocoa solids, cocoa butter, and sugar. It differs from any others chocolate in that it contains a higher percentage of cocoa solids and less sugar. In commercial dark chocolate, the solid cocoa content ranges from 47% (sweet dark) to 55%, 70%, 75%, or even above 90% for highly dark chocolate (Jacimovic et al., 2022).

The consumer importance of chocolate is very high due to its delicacy and health benefits (Samanta et al., 2022). The health benefits of dark chocolate are primarily attributed to its high antioxidant content, particularly flavonoids and polyphenols. These antioxidants have been linked to potential benefits for heart health, cognitive function, and overall well-being. Additionally, dark chocolate contains essential minerals such as iron, magnesium, and copper, and provides a good source of fibre (Godocikova et al., 2017). Dark chocolate has several health benefits, including protection against heart disease, regulation of blood sugar and insulin dependence, stroke prevention, antioxidant protection, alleviation of cold and cough, reduced cancer risk, reduced risk of colon cancer, slowing aging, increased immune function, Alzheimer's protection, reduction of premenstrual syndrome and prevention of alopecia (Samanta et al., 2022; Godocikova et al., 2017; Naz et al., 2014). Chocolate is also effective in increasing overall longevity, sexual appetite, and fertility. It has been associated with several health benefits due to its high cocoa content. Cocoa has the highest flavanol content of all foodstuffs on a weight basis and therefore is a significant contributor to the total dietary intake of flavonoids (Naz et al., 2014).

Literature review emphasizes the importance of fortified chocolate with functional ingredients, with the aim of enhancing its nutritional properties and sensory quality. The functional ingredient was omega-3 fatty acids obtained from flaxseed oil (Gultekin-Ozguven et al., 2016), fish oil capsules (Razavizadeh et al., 2024) and encapsulated chia seeds (Mexis et al., 2010). The structural integrity and consumer acceptance was of appreciable amounts with upto 10% fortification. Other studies highlighted that the addition of mulberry extracts, peanut skin, sea buckthorns to chocolate enhanced the antioxidant profile of the chocolates (Pastore et al., 2016; Al-Marazeeq, 2018). Chocolate was also used as a medium to incorporate iron, vitamin D3, carotenoids and protein from different innovative sources (Dean et al., 2016; Ekantari et al., 2019; Didar, 2021). Different analytical parameters and sensory panel

confirmed that the texture, flavor and stability of the chocolates were retained even after fortification and thus the functional ingredients can be used to produce functional confectionery.

However, dark chocolate can also be bitter and may not be to everyone's taste. One way to enhance its flavour and nutritional profile is by fortifying it with natural fruit juices. Watermelon and Sweet lime (sweet lime) fruit juices are rich in vitamins, minerals, and antioxidants that can complement the nutritional profile of dark chocolate.

Watermelon is a valued source of natural antioxidants with special reference to lycopene, ascorbic acid and citrulline. These functional ingredients act as protection against chronic health problems like cancer insurgence and cardiovascular disorders (Ozcelik and Yavuz, 2016). Watermelon contains phenolic, which are mainly hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives and a large amount of lycopene giving its characteristic red color and powerful antioxidant activity (Banerjee & Pal, 2021).

Watermelon juice contains various nutrients, including vitamin C, vitamin A, potassium, lycopene, and citrulline, which can help to improve immune function, better heart health, and potentially protect against certain diseases. Fortifying dark chocolate with watermelon juice can offer several health benefits due to the combination of nutrients from both ingredients.

For example, Watermelon juice contains lycopene, a powerful antioxidant that can help protect cells from damage caused by free radicals. When combined with the antioxidants found in dark chocolate, such as flavonoids, the overall antioxidant capacity of the fortified chocolate may be increased. This enhanced antioxidant protection can help reduce inflammation, support heart health, and potentially lower the risk of chronic diseases. The potassium content in watermelon juice, along with the flavonoids in dark chocolate, can support cardiovascular health. Potassium helps regulate blood pressure, while flavonoids have been linked to improved circulation and reduced risk of heart disease. The combination of these nutrients may have a synergistic effect on heart health, promoting better overall cardiovascular function (Banerjee & Pal, 2021).

On the other hand, sweet lime juice is regarded as one of the Indian superfoods due to its pharmacological effects, and is a rich source of various nutrients, including vitamin C, potassium, calcium, vitamin A, and dietary fibre. Sweet lime has been used to prevent scurvy, skin and hair issues, GI intolerance, constipation, type-II diabetes, ulcers, urinary tract infections, and, overall, boost innate immunity. Fortifying dark chocolate with sweet lime juice

can create a nutrient-rich food that offers a combination of vitamins, minerals, and antioxidants for improved health and well-being (Tolve et al., 2018).

Fortified dark chocolate with sweet lime juice has several benefits for health, such as providing enhanced protection against oxidative stress and inflammation, promoting better bone health and reducing the risk of osteoporosis, promoting healthy skin by supporting cell growth and repair, etc.

Fortifying dark chocolate with these fruit juices can add a unique and refreshing flavour while enhancing its nutritional value. The combination of dark chocolate with watermelon and sweet lime fruit juices can provide a delicious and healthy treat that appeals to a wider audience, including those who may not enjoy the bitterness of plain dark chocolate.

Fortifying dark chocolate with watermelon and sweet lime fruit juices can offer a unique and nutritious twist on a beloved treat. This project will explore the potential health benefits of this fortified dark chocolate, providing valuable insights into the development of innovative and healthier chocolate products.

This study aims to synthesize a dark chocolate fortified with watermelon and sweet lime juice to mask its bitterness. A comprehensive nutritional analysis of the newly developed product, including assessments of proximate composition, total polyphenol content, antioxidant content, minerals content, will be performed to determine its potential health benefits. The nutritional analysis will be followed by a sensory evaluation to assess the taste, texture, aroma and overall acceptance of the fortified dark chocolate, comparing them with traditional counterparts and identifying any sensory enhancements.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study was conducted to make fortified chocolate with watermelon and sweet lime juice and to assess its nutritional value. Five samples had been analysed for nutritional composition — (a) control sample (b) 4 test samples with three different sweetening agent combinations.

Materials

The chocolate samples evaluated in this study were made of Commercial Dark chocolate (55%), enriched with Watermelon juice and sweet lime juice. Dark chocolate (55%) was purchased from local market. Brown sugar, Jaggery, and Honey were used as sweetening agents. For control, plain dark chocolate (55%) was used. Enrichment ingredients and their addition are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Composition of fortified chocolate

Code of product	Ingredients					
	Watermelon juice	Sweet lime juice	Brown sugar	Jaggery	Honey	Dark Chocolate (55%)
Control	—	—	—	—	—	100%
A	29.04%	29.04%	13.7%	13.7%	—	14.52%
B	29.04%	29.04%	27.4%	—	—	14.52%
C	29.04%	29.04%	—	27.4%	—	14.52%
D	29.04%	29.04%	9.13%	9.13%	9.13%	14.52%

Chemicals

All chemicals were of analytical grade.

Chocolate preparation

Firstly, watermelon juice and sweet lime juice were extracted. The dark chocolate (55%) was melted in a double boiler, stirring until smooth. Once the chocolate was melted, the desired amount of sweet lime and watermelon fruit juice was added to the melted chocolate, stirring continuously to combine the ingredients. Four types of chocolate were prepared, containing the same amount of watermelon and sweet lime juice but different sweetening agents and their combinations are used in them, viz., one with only sugar, one with jaggery only, one with jaggery and sugar, and the last one with sugar, jaggery, and honey. The ratio of all other ingredients and the sweetening agent is the same in all types of chocolate. After mixing all ingredients, the chocolate was moulded using plastic moulds and then the prepared chocolate cubes were left to cool and solidify at room temperature. Figure 1 depicts the method of preparation of the experimental chocolates.

Figure 1. Flowchart of fortified chocolate process

Sample extract preparation

0.5 g of the sample was extracted with 10ml of 70% ethanol for two hours in a Falcon and vortexed frequently. The mixture was then filtered, and the filtrate was used for measurement. There was no lipid removal from the sample. Lipids from chocolate have been eliminated in most of the research; certain studies in the literature did not do so. All analyses were done thrice.

Proximate analysis of Samples

Determination of Moisture Content

The moisture of the sample was determined using the hot air oven method. 1g of each product was used to measure under 110 °C temperature (Sanchez-Moreno et al., 1998).

Determination of Ash content

Total Ash content was measured by igniting 3g of each sample for 5 hours at about 600° C temperature in a muffle furnace (Sanchez-Moreno et al., 1998).

Determination of Fat Content

Fat content was estimated using cold extraction method by using hexane solvent (Singleton & Rossi, 1965).

Determination of Fiber Content

To determine the crude fibre, 5g of the sample was mixed with 10 ml of petroleum ether to remove fat. After extraction with ether, boil 5g of dried sample with 100 ml of 0.25 N sulphuric acid for 30 minutes. Filter the mixture and wash with water until the washing is no longer acidic. Then the residue was collected in a beaker and boiled with 100 mL of Sodium hydroxide (0.25 N) solution for 30 minutes. Again, the mixture was filtered, and the residue was collected and dried. The dried sample was weighed and transferred to a silica crucible and ignited in a muffle furnace for 1 hour at 600° C (Sanchez-Moreno et al., 1998).

Determination of Carbohydrate Content

The carbohydrate of the sample was determined by the anthrone method. 10mg of each sample was hydrolysed by heating in a boiling water bath for 1 hour with 5ml of 2.5 M hydrochloric acid. After cooling, the mixture was neutralised with sodium carbonate and the volume was made up to 100 ml and the supernatant was collected, about 1ml. Then, 4 mL of anthrone reagent was added, and the sample absorbance was measured at 630 nm using a spectrophotometer (Sanchez-Moreno et al., 1998).

Determination of Protein Content

Protein content of the sample extract was determined by the Lowry's Method. 4 μ L of each sample extract was added with 96 μ L of 0.9% sodium chloride solution and 1ml Lowry's reagent was added to them. After 10 minutes of incubation in room temperature, 100 μ L of Folin-Ciocalteu solution was added to them and incubated for 30 minutes. Absorbance was determined at 620 nm (Sanchez-Moreno et al., 1998; Singleton & Rossi, 1965).

Determination of Antioxidant Content

DPPH scavenging activity

Radical scavenging activity of samples was measured using 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH). The sample extract was taken in different concentrations (10 μ L,20 μ L,50 μ L,100 μ L,500 μ L) and filled up to 1ml with 70% ethanol. Then 750ul mixture was pipetted and mixed with 250 μ L DPPH solution in a dark room. The spectrophotometer

was used to measure the sample's extract absorbance after 30 minutes of incubation at room temperature at 517nm (Barma et al., 2021).

Reducing Activity

To determine the reducing activity of the sample, different concentrations (10 μ L, 20 μ L, 50 μ L, 100 μ L, 500 μ L) of the sample extract were taken and filled up to 1ml with distilled water. 2.5ml PBS (phosphate buffer -0.2M) and 2.5 ml of 1% potassium ferricyanide were combined with one ml of the sample extract mixture. After giving the mixture a good stir, it was incubated at 50 °C for 20 minutes. After incubation, 2.5ml of 10% trichloroacetic acid (TCA) was added. After pipetting 2.5 ml of the mixture into the test tube, 0.5ml of 0.1% ferric chloride solution was added. Absorbance at 700nm was measured using the spectrophotometer (Cervellati et al., 2008).

Determination of Total Polyphenol Content

Folin-Ciocalteu reagent was used to measure the total polyphenol content. A sample extract in volume of 200 μ L was mixed with 600 μ L distilled water and 200 μ L of Folin reagent. After 5min incubation at room temperature 1ml of 8% sodium carbonate and 3ml of distilled water were added. Using a spectrophotometer, the absorbance at 765nm was determined after 30 minutes of resting in a dark area (Vertuani et al., 2014).

Determination of Mineral Content

Minerals (Calcium, Potassium, Sodium) content of the sample was measured using a photoelectric flame photometer. Volatilize the organic contents, 5 g of each sample was taken in a petri dish and kept in a hot air oven for 1hour at 110 °C temperature. Then the samples were transferred in silica crucible in a muffle furnace at 600 °C temperature till the ash was white in colour. 20 ml of dilute hydrochloric acid (1:1) was added to the ash and heated over a water bath for 30 minutes with a cover and 30 minutes without a cover. After heating, 5ml of dilute hydrochloric acid (1:1) was added again and the solution was filtered. After filtration, the volume was made up to 100 ml with distilled water. This solution was then placed in a photoelectric flame photometer to measure the calcium, potassium, and sodium content in the sample (Sanchez-Moreno et al., 1998).

Sensory Evaluation

Twenty participants had participated in the hedonic test of age groups 16-50 years, to gauge consumer approval of chocolate goods both with and without fruit juice fortification. A score was used to determine the panelist's degree of preference for the product.

Statistical analysis

All measurements and analyses were carried out thrice. Data were statistically analysed. The Microsoft™ Excel® application was used to assess experimental data using fundamental statistical variability markers. The linear correlation analysis was used to express the dependence rate between the examined features.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The pictures of the different formulations of dark chocolate are given below:

FIGURE 2: Pictures of the prepared chocolates

Changes in Proximate composition of Fortified chocolate

Proximate analysis for control dark chocolate (55%) and Fortified dark chocolate with Watermelon and Sweet lime juice with different sweeteners is portrayed in Table 2. The moisture, ash, fat, crude fibre, carbohydrate, and protein content were found to be as follows:

Table 2. Proximate composition of the Fortified chocolates

Parameters	Control	A	B	C	D
Moisture Content(%)	3.69 ± 0.11	20.91 ± 0.11	21.48 ± 0.09	22.12 ± 0.12	23.08 ± 0.08
Ash content (%)	0.93 ± 0.01	1.56 ± 0.02	1.63 ± 0.06	1.65 ± 0.09	1.73 ± 0.01
Fat	34.6 ± 0.06	25.20 ± 0.12	25.18 ± 0.10	25.17 ± 0.18	25.08 ± 0.15

Content (%)					
Crude fiber Content (%)	0.18 ± 0.02	0.21 ± 0.01	0.21 ± 0.01	0.21 ± 0.02	0.21 ± 0.02
Carbohydrate Content (%)	55.0 ± 0.08	49.02 ± 0.18	48.35 ± 0.22	47.68 ± 0.11	46.69 ± 0.10
Protein Content (%)	5.60 ± 0.11	3.10 ± 0.10	3.15 ± 0.20	3.17 ± 0.20	3.21 ± 0.20

Moisture content of fortified chocolate

Moisture content of all samples is shown in Table 2. Moisture Content was found in higher amounts in test samples than control due to watermelon and sweet lime juices containing a significant amount of water. When these juices are added to chocolate, they increase the final product's moisture content. Sweeteners like brown sugar, honey, and jaggery can also contain water, contributing to the moisture levels (Didar, 2021).

Ash content of fortified chocolate

Ash content of all samples is shown in Table 2. Ash content in food generally refers to the total mineral content after combustion. Watermelon and sweet lime fruit juices, along with jaggery and brown sugar, contain various minerals (like calcium, iron, zinc, magnesium, etc.) that can increase the ash content. Thus, ash content is higher in fortified chocolates than control (Didar, 2021).

Fat content of fortified chocolate

The fat content of all samples is shown in Table 2. Dark chocolate typically has a high cocoa butter content, which is a source of fat. When juices and other liquid ingredients are added to chocolate, they can dilute the overall fat content. The addition of watermelon and sweet lime juice reduces the proportion of cocoa butter in the final product. Thus, the fat content of the control was higher than that of the test samples (Singleton & Rossi, 1965).

Crude fibre content of fortified chocolate

Crude fibre content of all samples is shown in Table 2. Watermelon and sweet lime juices have some fiber, although they are primarily liquid. The pulp or other fibrous parts of the fruits are included in the fortification process, which can increase fibre content. The fibre is more in fortified chocolate than in the control.

Carbohydrate content of fortified chocolate

The carbohydrate content of all samples is shown in Table 2. Watermelon and sweet lime juices are primarily water and contain fewer carbohydrates. Brown sugar, jaggery, and honey are carbohydrate-rich substances. Due to the addition of liquid juices, the carbohydrate content slightly decreased in fortified chocolate in comparison to the control (Singleton & Rossi, 1965).

Protein content of fortified chocolate

Protein content of all samples is shown in Table 2. Watermelon juice and sweet lime juice have very low protein content. Dark chocolate does contain some protein from cocoa solids. Due to the addition of juices, the relative proportion of cocoa solids decreases, and the protein content of fortified dark chocolate becomes lower than that of control chocolate (Singleton & Rossi, 1965).

Polyphenol Content (mgGAE/g) in Fortified Chocolate**Table 3.** Total Polyphenol Content (mgGAE/g)

Control	A	B	C	D
1.189	1.466	1.118	1.2515	1.3745
± 0.052	± 0.005	± 0.438	± 0.059	± 0.039

The total Polyphenol Content values are presented in Table 3. Dark chocolate is already rich in polyphenols, particularly flavonoids. Watermelon and sweet lime juice contain various polyphenols, including flavonoids and phenolic acids. The addition of polyphenol-rich fruit juices can complement and enhance the overall polyphenolic profile of the fortified chocolate. Sample enriched with sweet lime and watermelon juice, along with different sweeteners, had more polyphenol content than the control sample (Singleton & Rossi, 1965).

Antioxidant content of fortified chocolate

DPPH Scavenging Activity

Table 4. Antioxidant Content measured by DPPH Scavenging activity

Concentrations	Control	A	B	C	D
S¹ (10 ul)	0.033 ± 0.052	0.082 ± 0.052	0.0875 ± 0.036	0.1095 ± 0.086	0.119 ± 0.014
S² (30 ul)	0.044 ± 0.006	0.0915 ± 0.011	0.0705 ± 0.009	0.154 ± 0.019	0.146 ± 0.009
S³ (50 ul)	0.052 ± 0.051	0.099 ± 0.014	0.0585 ± 0.016	0.163 ± 0.007	0.164 ± 0.024
S⁴ (100 ul)	0.063 ± 0.044	0.1135 ± 0.025	0.0735 ± 0.04	0.166 ± 0.003	0.1715 ± 0.009
S⁵ (500 ul)s	0.131 ± 0.002	0.1975 ± 0.029	0.11 ± 0.027	0.1865 ± 0.008	0.182 ± 0.004

The most common method for assessing a food's antioxidant capability is DPPH radical analysis. Our sample's antioxidant activity as determined by this technique is demonstrated in Table 4. Watermelon contains vitamins A and C, as well as lycopene, which are known for their antioxidant properties. Sweet lime Juice high in vitamin C and flavonoids, contributing additional antioxidants. Honey is rich in flavonoids and phenolic acids, which are powerful antioxidants. The combination of these ingredients may create a synergistic effect, where the antioxidants from different sources work together, enhancing the overall antioxidant capacity beyond what each ingredient could provide individually. In this result, the total DPPH content in the test samples was compared to the control sample (Cervellati et al., 2008; Vertuani, et al., 2014;; Aadil, 2014).

Reducing activity

Table 5. Antioxidant Content measured by Reducing Activity

Concentrations	Control	A	B	C	D
S¹ (10 ul)	0.936 ± 0.003	1.237 ± 0.052	1.163 ± 0.064	1.159 ± 0.188	1.199 ± 0.376
S²	1.138	1.404	1.276	1.432	1.433

(30 ul)	± 0.021	± 0.056	± 0.065	± 0.072	± 0.246
S³	1.492	1.515	1.340	1.586	1.511
(50 ul)	± 0.002	± 0.169	± 0.178	± 0.098	± 0.071
S⁴	1.525	1.689	1.568	1.747	1.871
(100 ul)	± 0.050	± 0.351	± 0.172	± 0.148	± 0.092
S⁵	1.906	2.045	1.977	2.185	2.245
(500 ul)	± 0.001	± 0.889	± 0.369	± 0.556	± 0.446

One important measure of a compound's potential antioxidant capability is its reducing activity. The primary mechanism of phenolic antioxidant effect, electron-donating activity, provides the basis for the reducing activity assay. Table 4 shows the reducing activity of the examined sample. Enrichment of dark chocolate with Watermelon and sweet lime juice showed improvement in antioxidant activity (Cervellati et al., 2008; Vertuani, et al., 2014;; Aadil, 2014).

Mineral Content in Fortified chocolate

Table 6. Minerals content of dark chocolate

Minerals	Control	A	B	C	D
Sodium (Na)	13.02±0.90	32.54±0.33	41.32±0.99	23.83±1.12	30.19±0.45
Calcium (Ca)	50.29±0.34	145.0±0.56	100.20±1.04	180±0.89	130±0.22
Potassium (K)	20.07±1.09	67.23±0.99	100.70±1.11	65.25±0.66	83.37±1.09

Table 6 shows the mineral content. Watermelon contains potassium, sodium and magnesium and sweet lime juice is rich in calcium and potassium. Sweetener ingredients like brown sugar also have minerals. The addition of these specific ingredients increases the mineral content of dark chocolate due to their inherent nutritional properties and lower levels of processing compared to standard dark chocolate (Cinquanta et al., 2016).

Organoleptic Evaluation

The prepared Dark chocolate samples were organoleptically evaluated on the basis of 10 points. Dark Chocolate was evaluated with respect to different sensory parameters, colour and appearance, flavour, taste, texture, and overall acceptability by the 20 panel members. Sensory score of samples is presented in the following Table 7.

Table 7. Organoleptic Evaluation

	Sensory Attributes				
	Colour & Appearance	Flavour	Taste	Texture	Overall acceptability
Control	7.8	5.2	5.0	8.9	5.6
A	9.0	9.0	9.2	8.5	9.2
B	8.7	8.3	8.0	8.2	8.5
C	8.1	8.0	8.4	6.7	8.8
D	8.4	8.4	8.9	6.6	8.9

CONCLUSION

Based on above mentioned analysis and result we can draw a conclusion that dark chocolate is generally a very good source of dietary antioxidants and physiologically active chemicals. Fortification Of dark chocolate with watermelon and sweet lime juice along with different sweeteners (brown sugar, jaggery, honey) increase its moisture, ash ,fibre, polyphenol, DPPH, Reducing Activity, minerals contents, while decreased fat, protein, carbohydrate contents. The increased levels of polyphenols and antioxidant activity suggest that the fortified dark chocolate may offer enhanced health benefits, including improved antioxidant capacity. The study demonstrates that fortifying dark chocolate with these natural ingredients can lead to a product that is not only more nutritious, provides a unique flavour but also positions as a functional food and may also offer additional health benefits compared to traditional dark chocolate.

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